

Synthesis of (N-Aryl-N-1,3,4,5-Tetrahydro-2,4-Dioxo-2H-1,5-Benzodiazepin-3-yl) Arylsulphonamides and (N-Aryl-N-1,2,3,4,6,7-Hexahydro-5,7-Dioxo-5H-1,4-Diazepin-6-yl) Aryl-Sulphonamides

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N-arylsulphonamides (Ia-I f) were condensed with diethyl- α -bromomalonate, and the condensates (IIa-II f) were reacted with *o*-phenylenediamine and 1,2-diaminoethane separately to afford (N-aryl-N-1,3,4,5-tetrahydro-2,4-dioxo-2H-1,5-benzodiazepin-3-yl) arylsulphonamides(IIIa-III f) and (N-aryl-N-1,2,3,4,6,7-hexahydro-5,7-dioxo-6H-1,4-diazepin-6-yl) arylsulphonamides (IVa-IV f) respectively. IIIa was also rearranged to 3-[2'-(benzenesulphonyl) anilino]-1,3,4,5-tetrahydro-2H-1,5-benzodiazepin-2,4-dione(V). The structures were established on the basis of elemental analyses and Nmr studies.

AS potent CNS drugs, diazepam and its related compounds are useful as tranquilizer, muscle relaxant, psychosedative, anticonvulsant, antihistaminic etc.¹⁻³ but there are some side effects like producing drowsiness. It was, therefore, thought worthwhile to synthesise N-heteryl-N-arylsulphonamides with 1,4-diazepine and 1,5-benzodiazepine as heterocyclic moieties in order to get better activity.

N-arylsulphonamides(Ia-I f) were condensed with diethyl- α -bromomalonate in DMF in presence of anhydrous K_2CO_3 when the condensates (IIa-II f) were obtained. IIa-II f were refluxed with *o*-phenylenediamine for 8-10 hr in HCl (4*N*) and on basification (10% NaOH), (IIIa-III f) were obtained and their structures were established as (N-aryl-N-1,3,4,5-tetrahydro-2,4-dioxo-2H-1,5-benzodiazepin-3-yl) aryl sulphonamides. Under similar conditions (IIa-II f) were reacted with 1,2-diamino-ethane to yield (N-aryl-N-1,2,3,4,6,7-hexahydro-5,7-dioxo-5H-1,4-diazepin-6-yl) arylsulphonamides(IVa-IV f).

An attempt was made to rearrange IB to the corresponding sulphone by treating it with conc. H_2SO_4 . The product obtained (V) was found to contain secondary amino groups thus indicating that the desired rearrangement had taken place. But the yield was not satisfactory. The structure of V was established as 3-[2'-(benzenesulphonyl) anilino]-1,3,4,5-tetrahydro-2H-1,5-benzodiazepin-2,4-dione.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. Nmr spectra of the compounds were recorded on varian A-60D model using TMS as internal reference and $CDCl_3$ as solvent.

Diethyl- α -(N-Phenylbenzenesulphonamido) malonate (IIa) :

A mixture of Ia(4.66 g., 0.020 mol), diethylmalonate (5.24 g., .022 mol) and DMF (25 ml) after stirring for 3 hr at 20-25°, was refluxed till the evolution of CO_2 ceased (7 hr). After removing DMF under reduced pressure (0.5 mm) the residue was extracted with $CHCl_3$ and the solvent layer dried over anh. Na_2SO_4 . On distilling off the solvent, the malonate(IIa) (5.48 g, 70%) was obtained as a thick brown oil.

Under similar conditions sulphonamides(Ib-I f) were reacted with diethyl- α -bromomalonate when the corresponding intermediates (IIb-II f) were obtained ; IIb, 68.24% ; IIc, 71.2% ; II d, 69.28% ; IIe, 70.82% ; II f, 67.86%.

(N-Phenyl-N-1,3,4,5-tetrahydro-2,4-dioxo-2H-1,5-benzodiazepin-3-yl) benzenesulphonamide(IIIa) :

IIa (3.90 g., 0.01*M*) was refluxed for 8 hr with *o*-phenylenediamine (2.16 g, 0.02*M*) in 4*N* HCl (20 ml) with continuous stirring. After cooling, the reaction mixture was basified with 10% NaOH. As the sticky mass did not solidify, it was converted to its hydrochloride (IIIa. HCl, m.p. 250°d ; yield, 2.17 g, 49.14%) (Found C, 56.52 ; H, 4.26 ; N, 9.67. Calcd. for : $C_{21}H_{17}O_4N_3S.HCl$, C, 56.82 ; H, 4.05 ; N, 9.47%).

Similarly, IIb-II f were reacted, with *o*-phenylenediamine to yield IIIb-III f. These compounds were converted to their hydrochlorides (IIIb, HCl, m.p, 268°d, yield 46.04% ; IIIc. HCl, 263°d ; 48.27% ; III d. HCl, 278°d, 49.24% ; IIIe. HCl, 270°d, 50.02% ; III f. HCl, 282°d, 49%).

(N-Phenyl-N-1,2,3,4,6,7-hexahydro-5,7-dioxo-5H-1,4-diazepin-6-yl) benzenesulphonamide(IVa).

IIa (1.95 g, 0.05 M) was refluxed with 1,2-diamino-ethane in 4N HCl (10 ml) for 10 hr. The

contents were cooled and basified (10% NaOH) when a sticky precipitate was obtained. It was converted to its hydrochloride (IVa. HCl, m.p. 195°d, yield 0.88 g, 44.56%) (Found : C, 51.86 ; H, 4.76 ; N, 10.30 ; Calcd. for : C₁₇H₁₇O₄N₂S. HCl : C, 51.58 ; H, 4.55 ; N, 10.61%).

Similarly IIb-IIf were reacted with 1,2-diamino-ethane and compounds IVb-IVf were isolated as their hydrochlorides (IVb. HCl, m.p. 210°d, yield 48.21% ; IVc. HCl, 205°d, 47.60% ; IVd. HCl, 215°d, 44.50% ; IVe, 220°d, 43.84% ; IVf. HCl, 230°d, 46.46%).

3-[2'-(Benzenesulphonyl)anilino]-1,3,4,5-tetra-hydro-2H-benzodiazepin-2,4-dione(V) :

IIIa (1.01 g, 0.0025M) was added to H₂SO₄ (5.0 ml, sp. gr. 1.84) in one lot. The contents were kept over water bath for 3 min. and poured in crushed ice to yield V which on treatment with ethereal HCl afforded its hydrochloride (V, HCl, m.p. 271°d ; yield 0.34 g, 30.66%) (Found : C, 57.20 ; H, 3.86 ; N, 9.26 Calcd. for : C₂₁H₁₇O₄N₂S. HCl ; C, 56.82 ; H, 4.05 t N, 9.47%).

Structural elucidation

In the Nmr spectra of compounds IIa-IIIf, IIIa-IIIf, IVa-IVf and V the chemical shift, expressed in δ ppm, have been compiled in Tables 1-2.

TABLE 1—Nmr SPECTRA OF COMPOUNDS(II)

Compound Number	Molecular formula	ArH(m)	enolic -OH(bs)*	-N-OH(s)*	2-COOCH ₂ (q)	2-CH ₂ -CH ₂ (t)	Ar-OCH ₃ (s)	Ar-CH ₃ (s)
IIa	C ₁₈ H ₂₁ O ₄ NS	6.8-8.1(10H)	4.9	2.6	4.0] ⁴ H 4.35]	1.00] ⁶ H 1.92]		
b	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ O ₄ NS	6.8-8.0(9H)	4.95	2.55	4.15] ⁴ H 4.35]	1.00] ³ H 1.32]		2.25] ³ H 2.35]
c	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ O ₇ NS	6.6-8.2(9H)	5.05	2.8	4.18] ⁴ H 4.45]	1.00] ³ H 1.37]	3.7] ³ H 3.8]	
d	C ₂₁ H ₂₅ O ₇ NS	6.6-8.1(8H)	5.05	2.7	4.18] ⁴ H 4.45]	1.18] ⁶ H 1.6]	3.7] ³ H 3.8]	2.35] ³ H 2.45]
e	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ O ₆ NS	6.6-8.15(9H)	5.05	2.4	4.15] ⁴ H 4.45]	1.05] ³ H 1.45]		2.05] ³ H 2.25]
f	C ₂₁ H ₂₅ O ₆ NS	6.6-8.1(8H)	5.05	2.5	4.15] ⁴ H 4.45]	1.05] ³ H 1.40]		2.05] ³ H 2.25] 2.45]

s=singlet, q=quartet, t=triplet, b=broad, m=multiplet.

* The peaks due to enolic OH and -NCH- together integrate for one proton.

TABLE 2—Nmr SPECTRA FOR COMPOUNDS III AND IV

Compound Number	Molecular formula	-NH(bs)	ArH(m)	Enolic-OH (bs)	Ar-OCH ₃ (s)	CH ₃ (bs)	Ar-CH ₃ (s)
IIIa	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₂ S	9.55(2H)	7.05-8.05(14H)	6.5-6.8(1H)	-	-	-
b	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₂ S	9.55(2H)	7.0-8.1(13H)	6.5-6.8(1H)	-	-	1.82(3H)
c	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₂ S	9.55(2H)	6.95-8.0(13H)	6.5-6.8(1H)	3.5(3H)	-	-
d	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₂ S	9.35(2H)	7.0-8.1(12H)	6.5-6.8(1H)	3.75(3H)	-	2.4(3H)
e	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₂ S	9.35(2H)	7.0-8.0(13H)	6.5-6.8(1H)	-	-	2.1(3H)
f	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₂ S	9.55(2H)	7.0-8.1(12H)	6.5-6.8(1H)	-	-	2.0(3H) 2.25(3H)
IVa	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₂ S	9.45(2H)	7.0-8.0(10H)	6.5-6.8(1H)	-	3.2-3.6(4H)	-
b	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₂ S	9.5(2H)	6.9-8.1(9H)	6.5-6.8(1H)	-	3.15-3.65(4H)	2.30(3H)
c	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₂ S	9.5(2H)	6.8-8.1(9H)	6.5-6.8(1H)	3.75(3H)	3.2-3.5(4H)	-
d	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₂ S	9.4(2H)	7.0-8.0(8H)	6.5-6.8(1H)	3.70(3H)	3.2-3.5(4H)	2.95(3H)
e	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₂ S	9.45(2H)	7.0-8.1(9H)	6.5-6.8(1H)	-	3.2-3.65(4H)	2.1(3H)
f	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₂ S	9.5(2H)	6.9-8.1(8H)	6.5-6.8(1H)	-	3.2-3.6(4H)	2.2(3H) 2.4(3H)
V	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₂ S	9.5(3H)	6.9-8.1(13H)	6.5-6.8(1H)	-	-	-

s=singlet, bs=broad, m=multiplet.

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